

SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF TRACE AMOUNTS OF SILVER(I) IONS USING H-RESORCINOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17336892>

Relevance: A new organic reagent, H-resorcinol, was employed as a highly sensitive, selective, and rapid-acting reagent for the determination of silver (I) ions. The interaction of silver (I) with H-resorcinol occurs through the formation of a stable coordination bond. At pH = 10, an ammonia buffer solution was used as a background electrolyte, resulting in the formation of a 1:1 (silver:H-resorcinol) molar ratio complex. This approach is of particular importance, as the reliable and selective determination of trace silver ions holds significant analytical value in environmental monitoring, pharmaceutical analysis, and industrial quality control, where the accurate detection of even very low concentrations of silver is essential.

Purpose of the study: The determination of Silver (I) ion with H-resorcinol as an organic reagent expands the possibilities of analytical chemistry. The IR spectrum of the obtained complex confirmed the coordination bond formation.

Materials and methods: A spectrophotometric microanalytical method was applied. The complex formation was carried out at pH=10, in an ammonia buffer solution. The composition of the complex was studied using IR spectroscopy. The IR spectrum was analyzed by studying the main vibrations (stretching and deformation vibrations), and the coordination of silver was confirmed through group vibrations.

Results: The IR spectrum of the complex showed the following absorption bands: 3327 cm⁻¹ (broad peak, N–H stretching vibration), 2921 cm⁻¹ and 2853 cm⁻¹ (aliphatic C–H stretching vibration), 2241 cm⁻¹ (–C≡N stretching vibration), 1651 cm⁻¹ and 1541 cm⁻¹ (C=O and C=N stretching vibrations), 1493 cm⁻¹ and 1339 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C and C–N stretching vibrations), 1193 cm⁻¹ and 1036 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C and C–N stretching vibrations), 813 cm⁻¹, 596 cm⁻¹, 509 cm⁻¹, and 493 cm⁻¹ (metal–ligand vibrations, Ag–N and Ag–O coordination bonds). These results confirm the coordination of silver ions with the ligand (H-resorcinol)

Conclusions: H-resorcinol is a suitable organic reagent for the determination of silver (I) ions. The obtained IR spectral data confirmed the coordination of silver ions with the functional groups of H-resorcinol, mainly via Ag–N and Ag–O coordination bonds. Due to the high sensitivity and selectivity of this method, silver (I) ion can be determined rapidly and accurately, even in trace amounts.